

IMPROVEMENT OF TAX CONTROL METHODOLOGY UNDER THE CONDITIONS OF QUALITATIVE TRANSFORMATIONS IN THE SYSTEM OF STATE TAX SERVICE BODIES

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Abstract. This article discusses the issues of reforming tax control, further improving and increasing the efficiency of state tax authorities, the formation of a “digital economy”, which is a logical continuation and development of the use of modern information and communication technologies as well as accelerating the implementation of universally recognized international norms and standards in national legislation.

Key words: Tax control, taxpayers, tax service employee, taxes, other mandatory payments, direct taxes, indirect taxes, resource payments, state budget, state tax authorities, investment climate, principles of tax control, tax administration, tax monitoring, cameral tax audit, field tax audit, tax audit.

Introduction

The ongoing work on the implementation of standards and recommendations of the World Trade Organization, the World Customs Organization, as well as other international organizations into national legislation requires the improvement of tax control and simplification of tax procedures.

Methods of combating smuggling and corruption, illegal currency transactions and tax evasion and other mandatory payments require the use of modern methods of tax control.

The implementation of the tasks of state regulation of the economy as an objective necessity largely depends on the budgetary possibilities of financing socio-economic projects, as well as on the active use by the state of instruments of influence on the interests of economic entities. Taxes and tax control play an important role in this.

In order to reform tax control, further improve and increase the efficiency of the activities of state bodies of the tax service, the formation of a "digital economy", which is a logical continuation and development of the use of modern information and communication technologies, as well as accelerate the implementation of generally accepted international norms and standards in the field of tax control into national legislation.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted in his message to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

"According to the recently adopted Tax Code, many innovations have been introduced since this year. In particular, the number of types of taxes has been reduced from 13 to 9. Simplified tax payment mechanisms with the possibility of deferral or installments have been introduced.

Every employee of the tax service, entrepreneurs, taxpayers should understand and apply the norms of the new Tax Code well, for this it is necessary to establish their regular training.

In order to radically change the attitude of tax service employees to their business and train qualified personnel, I propose to create a Fiscal Institute at the State Tax Committee and attract reputable foreign experts for this." [1]

Analysis of thematic literature

It is necessary to distinguish between the concepts of "tax control" and "tax administration". If tax control is part of the tax mechanism, then tax administration is part of taxation management.

Tax administration is one of the functions of state tax management (taxation management).

The purpose of tax administration is to achieve the maximum possible effect for the budget system from tax revenues at the lowest possible cost.

Tax control is a set of measures carried out by tax and other authorized bodies aimed at detecting violations of the current legislation on taxes and fees, as well as preventing them," as stated by M.M.Shadurskaya, E.A.Smorodina, T.V.Bakunova in his textbook on the essence and forms of tax control [2].

Chernik D.G. in his textbook on taxes and taxation believes that tax control is the control over the correctness of the payment of taxes and fees by legal entities and individuals. Tax control is understood as verification of compliance by taxpayers with the legislation on taxes and fees; identification of tax violations; ensuring the receipt of tax payments to the budget at all levels. The formation of tax policy is a set of measures that ensure timely and full payment of taxes and fees, in the amounts necessary to finance government activities.[3]

The methodology, forms and tools of tax control are reflected in the works of E.S. Vylkova, L.I. Goncharenko, A.Z. Dadashev, T.A. Efremova, V.A. Krasnitsky, Yu.M. Krokhina, I.I. Kucherov, O.A. Mironova, M.V. Mishustin, N.N. Nesterova, O.A. Nogina, K.V. Novoselov, S.G. Pepelyaev, A.V. Terzidi, F.F. Hanafeev, D.M. Shchekin.

The works of S.V. Barulin, A.V. Varnavsky, N.G. Vishnevskaya, V.A. Kashin, N.P. Melnikova, M.R. Pinskaya, O.S. Semenova, I.A.Ergashev, B.A.Normatov, U.A.

Berdiev, Sh.A.Allayarov are devoted to the problems of the organization of tax control taking into account the identification of tax risks. [4]

Research methodology

The methodological basis of the research is a systematic and analytical approach that allows us to present scientific studies of socio-economic phenomena and processes in their development, legislative and regulatory acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the development of tax control in the conditions of qualitative transformations in the system of state bodies of the tax service. In the course of writing this article, methods of systematic, logical, comparative and economic-mathematical analysis were used. Methods of exposure include: improvement of tax control and simplification of tax procedures and other measures of influence.

Research methodology it is very important that it is chosen correctly, because research methodology always occupies a key place. Referring to the task set by us to show the effectiveness of tax control and tax collection and the preparedness of the regulatory framework of Uzbekistan, we came to the conclusion that we will use methods of empirical and theoretical level, namely methods of study and generalization, analysis and synthesis, observation.

Analysis and results

An effective taxation system and well-coordinated work of the state tax service bodies are of particular importance in the context of the implementation of large-scale reforms for the long-term development of the country's economy.

The effectiveness of tax control and tax collection are predetermined by the macroeconomic conditions in which, on the one hand, taxpayers carry out economic activities, on the other hand, the tax authorities exercise the main powers of tax control.

Tax control is a complex and purposeful system of economic and legal actions of competent state authorities, which is based on legislation in the field of taxation.

The main direction of tax control is the collection and analysis of information on the fulfillment of taxpayers' obligations to pay taxes. It is also an important condition for the functioning of the tax system.

The growth of the state's financial needs requires the smooth functioning of the tax collection mechanism. In practice, the tax authorities reveal the facts of late payment of taxes and other mandatory payments by taxpayers, which is currently a problem for such parties to financial relations as the state and taxpayers. For this reason, the problem of efficiency and improvement of control over the correctness, timeliness and completeness of tax collection becomes acute.

The main task of the state bodies of the tax service is to improve tax control and the entire system of state bodies of the tax service as a whole, which, in turn, should lead to the elimination of existing problems in this area.

The need for tax control is caused by such negative qualities of individuals and legal entities as unconsciousness, improper temporary payment of taxes established by law and other mandatory payments in full.

Currently, one of the main tasks of the state bodies of the tax service is to monitor compliance with tax legislation. Ensuring the efficiency of the work of the state bodies of the tax service and improving tax control contribute to an increase in the receipts of tax and other mandatory payments in full. The development and improvement of tax control is a very time-consuming and lengthy process. After all, full tax control over the correctness of calculation and timely transfer of tax and other mandatory payments has not yet been implemented, and taxpayers' evasion from paying tax and other mandatory payments has also not been disclosed.

The Republic of Uzbekistan is implementing large-scale reforms in the areas of tax policy aimed at creating favorable conditions for entrepreneurship and improving the investment climate.

Figure 1. Receipt of payments to the budget for taxes as of October 1, 2020-2021 (billion soums).¹

At the same time, expert assessments and surveys conducted among business entities indicate that a high level of shadow turnover remains in the economy, especially in the areas of trade and catering, road transport, housing construction and repair, accommodation services, which infringes on the economic interests of bona fide entrepreneurs and creates unequal conditions for them to do business.

¹ Данные государственного налогового комитета Республики Узбекистан

In order to reduce the level of the shadow economy in the country, create equal competitive conditions for doing business, including by reducing the regulatory and administrative burden, automating procedures and simplifying the procedure for compliance with tax control requirements.[5]

The organization of the work of the state tax service bodies, based on outdated methods and principles of tax control, does not allow them to solve the new tasks assigned to them, including expanding the tax base and increasing tax collection, which is aggravated by the presence of significant unresolved problems.

1. Low level of tax administration, mainly related to the implementation of forecast indicators and limited to tax reporting without searching for additional sources of taxation.

2. Irrational use of information and communication technologies, which does not allow to fully implement tax administration, determine the additional tax base and reduce the level of shadow turnover in the economy.

3. The lack of effective software products that ensure the collection of external sources for in-house control.

4. Inefficiency of the use of the powers granted to control the activities of trade enterprises, public catering, markets and shopping complexes, leading to the creation of various tax evasion schemes.

5. The lack of clear criteria for identifying persons who systematically evade taxes for the organization of targeted inspections, as well as factors contributing to the commission of tax offenses.

The tax control system, like any system, interacts with the external environment, the challenges of which require internal coordination and configuration. The process of updating an object, bringing it into compliance with new conditions, requirements, quality indicators is called modernization.

Conclusion and suggestions

Control, being a management function, occupies an important place in the process of economic activity. At the macroeconomic level, the role of tax control is obvious in the composition of tax administration and the implementation of tax policy.

Improving tax control in the system of state bodies of the tax service should solve the following tasks:

1. Improving the methods of combating smuggling and corruption, illegal currency transactions and evasion of tax and other mandatory payments, the state tax service bodies should apply modern methods of tax control.

2. Improving the forms and mechanisms of tax control, including through the widespread introduction of modern information and communication technologies that provide the most complete coverage and accounting of taxable entities and taxpayers.

3. Professional development of employees of the state tax service and taxpayers.

4. Conduct free consultations on the most complex provisions of the Tax Code and tax legislation.

5. To provide free training programs on tax legislation.

6. Improving the efficiency of the activities of state bodies of the tax service should form a "digital economy", which is the continuation and development of the use of modern information and communication technologies.

Thus, the development of tax control at the level of economic entities has a mutual benefit for each of the parties to tax relations, and can become, on the one hand, one of the sources of increasing business efficiency, and on the other hand, a guarantee of the financial security of the state in terms of generating budget revenues.

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